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Achieving Net-Zero Emission Targets: Technologies and Economics

Govinda R Timilsina^{1†}

1 Senior Research Economist, Development Research Group, World Bank, Washington, DC, USA

† Corresponding author, gtimilsina@worldbank.org

Abstract: Since the Paris Climate Agreement set the global warming target well below 2°C, preferably 1.5°C relative to pre-industrial levels, many nations, sub-nations, and corporate entities have announced net-zero targets for carbon dioxide or greenhouse gas emissions. This study aims to understand the economic implications of net-zero targets by reviewing the existing body of literature. However, not many studies are found on the macroeconomic and distributional impacts of net-zero targets. Existing studies are rather focused on net-zero targets at the sectoral levels even though sectoral net-zero targets are sub-optimal. Most net-zero roadmaps rely on technologies that are not yet economically viable and commercially available, implying that the achievement of the net-zero targets is contingent on technological breakthroughs and cost reductions of the emerging technologies for zero emissions, energy storage, and carbon removal. The study stresses that government and corporate policies that played a critical role in reducing the costs of solar and wind power and their scaling-up, should be expanded to support the emerging technologies included in net-zero roadmaps. The study also highlights the need for further research on the economic and distributional consequences of net-zero targets and the policy design for achieving the targets.

Keywords: Climate change, Paris Climate Agreement, Net-zero emissions, clean technologies.

Main highlights: add four to six short sentences that capture the main takeaways of the paper. Each sentence should not exceed 100 characters.

- The Paris Climate Agreement aims to limit GHG concentration below 2°C to mitigate climate change
- Many nations have set up long-term net-zero emission targets for carbon neutral economy in this century
- Sub-national economies and corporate entities are setting net-zero targets independently
- Net-zero targets entail a massive transformation of the current energy supply and consumption patterns
- Net-zero targets envision commercialization of emerging technologies including hydrogen and CO₂ capture

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- Economic impacts of meeting net-zero targets yet to be assessed

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Introduction

Since the Paris Climate Agreement set the global warming target well below 2°C, preferably 1.5°C relative to pre-industrial levels, many nations, sub-nations, and corporate entities announced net-zero target for Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) or greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The net-zero emission targets are, however, aspirational. There is huge uncertainty on how to meet these targets. Many economies and corporations which set up net-zero emission targets have done so without a clear roadmap to meet the targets. Achievements of the targets are contingent on several conditions, particularly commercial availability of emerging technologies, such as carbon capture and storage (CCS) and utilization (CCUS), bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), green hydrogen, large-scale battery storage, direct atmospheric carbon capture and storage (DACCS). It requires a massive change in existing energy supply and utilization systems including electrification of all end-use energy systems and supplying entire electricity through zero-emission sources (Davis et al. 2018; van Vuuren et al. 2018; IEA 2021). It will also demand change in lifestyle with less and less carbon footprint in food-supply chains.

Achieving net-zero emissions will have massive economic implications. It might replace the entire fossil fuel energy sectors (i.e., coal, oil and refinery, natural gas production and processing) with non-fossil fuel energy sectors (i.e., hydropower and renewables, nuclear, biomass) unless CCS or CCUS are commercially available. On the end-use side, fossil fuels will be replaced with non-fossil fuels (electricity, hydrogen) implying replacing supply chains of fossil fuel-using vehicles, appliances, devices, and processes with electricity-using ones. To meet the net zero target by 2035, for example, Klaaßen and Steffen (2023) estimate that the EU will require €302 billion annual investment during the 2021–2025 period on top of what it would need otherwise. McKinsey & Company estimates investments needed in 69 countries around the world and reports that total investments on physical assets for energy and land-use systems in those countries between 2021 and 2050 would amount to about \$275 trillion (on average \$9.2 trillion annually) to achieve their net-zero targets (Krishnan et al. 2022). To achieve the net-zero targets, more investments would be made before 2030 than after (spending 6.8% of GDP in 2021 and gradually increasing to 8.8% of GDP by 2030 before falling). The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) estimates that achieving net zero emissions by 2050 would require \$103 trillion investment during the 2023 – 2050 period, or \$3.7 trillion annually over the next 27 years (IRENA, 2023).

How will these impacts be distributed across the countries and various production sectors and households within the countries? How will it change global trade patterns? The objective of this review is to help answer these questions by bringing insights from the relevant literature. A few existing reviews of literature analysing net zero emission targets in various countries (e.g., Bistline, 2021). However, the existing literature is concentrated on the pathways or roadmaps to achieve the net-zero targets instead of the economic implications of those roadmaps.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on economic and distributional impacts of pathways to achieve net-zero targets followed by highlights of the importance of some emerging technologies to achieve net-zero emission targets. Finally, key conclusions together with research gaps are highlighted in Section 4.

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2. Economic Impacts of Achieving Net-Zero Emission Targets

The economic impacts of net-zero emissions are assessed at different levels. Some studies (e.g., Jaumotte et al. 2021; Rogelj et al. 2018; Connolly et al. 2016; Bataille et al. 2020) investigate global or regional economic impacts of achieving net-zero emissions. Studies, such as Parry and Wingender (2021), Kemp et al. (2021), Williams et al. (2020), Glynn et al. (2019), and Duan et al. (2021) analyse macroeconomic implications of net-zero targets set by various countries.

The net-zero pathway developed by the IPCC (Rogelj et al. 2018) reports that renewable sources (bioenergy, hydro, wind, and solar) would supply 52% to 67% of global primary energy requirement, whereas coal with CCS would supply 1% to 7% by 2050. Energy supplied from oil and gas would be from facilities equipped with CCS and remaining emissions would be neutralized by carbon removals through biological sequestration. It also estimates that 59% to 97% electricity would be generated from renewables, and a reduction of a 4 million sq.km. to an increase of 2.5 million sq.km. of non-pasture agricultural land for food and feed crops. It would convert a 0.5 to 11 million sq.km. of pastureland into 0-6 million sq.km. of agricultural land for energy crops. The forest lands could be reduced 2 million sq.km. into 9.5 million sq.km. increase in forests. The additional energy related average investment needed to achieve the net-zero target is estimated to be \$830 billion (2010 price) annually during the 2016-2050 period from that in the baseline (i.e., without new climate policies since 2016). The IPCC report concludes that net-zero target can be achieved with reduced global poverty, improved energy security and large public health benefits through improved air quality.

Jaumotte et al. (2021) examines climate change mitigation strategies for achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 globally. The main policy it considers is carbon pricing with an initial green fiscal stimulus, which consists of green public investment and renewable electricity subsidies. Using the G-Cubed general equilibrium model, the study finds that green public spending can boost global output (relative to the baseline) for the first 15 years of the low-carbon transition. The starting carbon prices range from \$6 - \$20/tCO₂; they reach \$10 - \$40/tCO₂ in 2030, and \$40 - \$150/tCO₂ in 2050. The policy is found to cost the global economy moderately (1% loss of global GDP from the baseline in 2050). The key message from the study is that upfront green fiscal packages facilitate the smooth transition to a low-carbon economy. The results might have been influenced by several assumptions and costs seem to be highly underestimated.

Net-zero studies at the regional level includes ADB (2023) for the Asia & Pacific region, Bataille et al. (2020) for the Latin America region and Connolly et al. (2016) for the European Union. ADB (2023) sets a net-zero target for the region and pathways to achieve it by 2100. It shows that 44% of the total emissions reduction by 2050 would be achieved through energy efficiency improvement and 45% through clean energy sources. Electricity sector would be fully decarbonized by 2050 through the expansion of renewable energy sources and complete phasing out of coal-fired power generation. The net-zero emission target also require an increase of 95 million hectares (ha) of forest land or 30% of the total regional land cover by 2050. The net-zero emission target requires \$707 billion annual investment (1.5%–2.7% of regional GDP) by 2050. The economic costs of meeting the net-zero target is estimated to be less than 3% of GDP during the 21st century excluding the value of climate co-benefits. If

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climate co-benefits are accounted for, the net present value of benefits is found to be five times the cost in the region. Bataille et al. (2020) present a synthesis of country studies for achieving net zero emissions in six Latin America by 2050 in the energy, agriculture, forestry and land use (AFOLU) sectors. The study shows that electricity generation would increase by 182–428% in 2050 from the 2015 level to achieve net zero emissions in these countries. The share of electricity in the final energy demand would be 28% to 82% in 2050 as compared to 15% to 26% in 2015. Each country's electricity system will see mixes of wind, solar, hydro, nuclear, fossil fuels with CCS, and biomass with CCS, but at different proportions. They will undergo massive electrification of transportation. Biofuels also play a major role in the transport sector decarbonization in Colombia and Peru. Connolly et al. (2016) analyse the economics of achieving net zero emissions from the energy system (or 100% renewables for meeting the entire energy demand) in the EU by 2050. The energy supply system requires wind power, solar power, large-scale thermal storage, biomass gasification, CCR, electrolyzers, chemical synthesis, and fuel storage. It shows that a 100% renewable energy system is technically viable in Europe even without nuclear and unsustainable amounts of bioenergy. The overall cost of energy supply with 100% renewables would be approximately 10–15% higher than that in the business-as-usual case.

Since the net-zero targets are announced at the national level, several studies have analysed their economic impacts. Duan et al. (2021) analysed the economic impacts of China's path for meeting the global 1.5°C warming target, which is also consistent with China's net-zero targets set for the year 2060. It finds that meeting the global 1.5°C warming limit would cause China to reduce its GHG emissions by more than 90% (90 to 112%) by 2050. It corresponds to a reduction of CO₂ emissions by 51.3% to 85% and CH₄ and N₂O emissions by 24.1 to 68.8%. Achievement of the net zero targets is contingent on the large-scale deployment of CCS and BECCS. The study reports that the economic costs of the net-zero target (measured in terms of GDP loss in 2050 as compared to that in the baseline), would vary from 2.3% to 10.9% depending on the model used for the analysis. In terms of accumulated GDP by 2050, the loss will vary between 2.8% to 5.7%. Williams et al. (2021) analyse the costs of meeting the net-zero targets set by the US government for 2050 developing five scenarios. The central scenario is a least-cost carbon-neutral system with minimum constraints on decarbonization options. The incremental energy system costs under this scenario would be \$145 billion as compared to the baseline scenario in 2050, accounting for 0.4% of GDP in that year. If all energy is produced from renewables by 2050 thereby eliminating the use of fossil fuels and nuclear power, including for feedstocks (100% renewable scenario), the incremental costs would increase to 0.9% of GDP. If the least cost optimization options (central scenario) are accompanied by negative emissions of -500 Mt CO₂ in 2050, consistent with a 350 ppm or 1°C global trajectory in 2100 (net negative scenario), the incremental energy system cost in 2050 would be 0.6% of GDP in that year. The incremental capital investment for the energy system in the central scenario would be \$600 billion per year on average (for 30 years between 2020 and 2050). It accounts for 10% of the current U.S. total capital investment of \$6 trillion per year in all sectors. In an earlier study for the United States, Jacobson et al. (2015) presents roadmaps for each State in the US to meet the entire energy demand in the electricity, transportation, building, and industry sectors through renewables (100% renewables). Meeting entire end-use demand through electricity and producing all electricity through non-fossil sources boils down to net-zero CO₂ emissions from the energy system. The roadmap requires up to 85% replacement of existing energy supply facilities with renewables by 2030 and 100% by 2050 along with massive improvements in energy production and consumption efficiency. In 2050, the electricity load would be met by onshore

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wind (40%), utility-scale PV (31%), offshore wind (19%), and remaining by other renewables (e.g., concentrated and rooftop solar, hydro, geothermal). Glynn et al. (2019) analyse several scenarios for deep decarbonization of Ireland's energy system including scenarios for the 1.5°C target which is the net zero emission target. They find that the scenario that meets the net zero target and is technically feasible would be too expensive to the Irish economy as the CO₂ mitigation costs would exceed €8,100/tCO₂ by 2050. Ireland's economic output (i.e., GDP) will drop by 3.6%–5.2% in 2030 and 2.7%–3.9% by 2050. In a study for Finland, where more than 60% of current total energy demand is met through non-fossil fuels sources, Parry and Wingender (2021) finds that Finland would require a carbon tax that reaches €125 per ton by 2030 to meet the net-zero target by 2035. Vats and Mathur (2022) examine a path to achieve India's net zero targets in India by 2050. It shows that four sectors - agriculture, commercial, residential, and transport, can technically achieve net zero emissions by 2050. The power and industry sectors still need fossil fuel-based energy in 2050 and fossil fuels account for 21% of total primary energy supply in 2050. Thus, CCS and natural sinks (afforestation, wetlands, agroforestry, blue carbon, etc.) will be needed to achieve the net zero target. To achieve net zero emissions in 2050, India needs to reduce its emissions in absolute terms before 2030.

Some of the country climate and development reports (CCDRs) of the World Bank also estimate the economic impacts of achieving the net-zero targets (e.g., Brazil, China, Kazakhstan, South Africa) or to be moving in the deep decarbonization path in the next two decades to achieve the net-zero targets (e.g., Indonesia, Türkiye, Vietnam). Most of these CCDRs report positive economic impacts while achieving net-zero emission targets, which contradicts findings from other studies. Three factors can be attributed to the positive economic outputs while enrooting the deep decarbonization path to achieve the net-zero emission targets. These are: (i) availability of external financing for the low-carbon transition, (ii) increased economic efficiency through energy and labour market reforms anticipated in the low-carbon transition, (iii) accounting for co-benefits, particularly health benefits that can be realized through the reduction of local air pollution. The level of economic impacts of achieving the net-zero targets or remaining on the path of achieving them is different across the countries. The main reason could be the difference in economic structures and energy supply mixes across the countries. The differences in underlying assumptions while developing the baseline scenarios and net-zero paths might have also contributed to the varying level of economic impacts across the countries. In South Africa, for example, it is assumed that wind and solar account for 85% of total electricity generation in the baseline (or net-zero reference scenario). It is also assumed in the baseline that the South African economy will grow by 2.3% annually despite the deep decarbonization of the economy. It means that additional efforts required to achieve the net-zero targets are minimal. It is also assumed that the country would gain significantly from the exports of hydrogen whose production is financed through foreign investments.

It is also important to understand the distributional or equity implications of meeting the net-zero targets because these issues are very sensitive politically and socially. Careful analyses of distributional consequences (both vertically or by income and horizontally or by spatial angle) are necessary before the policies are set and roadmaps are developed for achieving net-zero targets. A study by Lenzi et al. (2021) examines the equity implications of three alternative pathways to achieve net-zero emissions globally. Under the first pathway, all countries are assumed to achieve net zero CO₂ emissions by 2050. Under the second pathway, the 38 OECD countries achieve net-zero CO₂ emissions around 2030 and

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developing countries achieve the target later. The third pathways, the 38 OECD countries achieve net zero CO₂ emissions by 2050, and non-OECD countries do the same later using carbon removal technologies at a large scale. Under each pathway, the cumulative CO₂ emissions over the century maintained at the level to meet the 1.5 °C global warming target. The study argues that developing countries will suffer the most under the first pathway unless they are compensated by substantial financial transfers from the developed world. This pathway will cause a significant cost to both developing and developed world due to the early retirement of fossil fuel infrastructures (stranded assets and lost value of fossil energy resources). The second pathway not only causes greater economic burdens to the OECD economies. The burdens might fall upon low-income populations due to increased energy and energy-intensive commodity prices resulting from the high carbon pricing and corresponding carbon border adjustment taxes (CBAT). The high levels of CBAT could substantially harm developing economies depending on emission-intensive exports. The third pathway, which reflects a more likely global net-zero scenario, implies additional costs needed for carbon removal technologies in the second half of the century. It will pass the climate change mitigation burden to the future generation in the developing world. It also poses a risk of overshooting the net-zero target if anticipated carbon removal technologies are not commercially available on time. This study does not offer any quantitative analysis. It is merely an opinion-based qualitative analysis. While the arguments look intuitive, their confirmation or verification through numerical analysis is necessary. For example, the side effects of the second pathway on the non-OECD countries could be much higher than anticipated here because this pathway could severely affect exports of fossil fuels and emission-intensive products from non-OECD countries.

There exist many studies analysing net-zero targets at the sectoral level such as the energy sector, power sector, transportation sector, manufacturing sector, building sector, and agriculture sector (IRENA, 2023; IEA, 2022; Cole et al. 2021; Capros et al. 2019; Handayani et al. 2022; Ball-Burack et al. 2022; Oshiro et al. 2018; Hafner et al. 2021; Panos et al. 2023; Kemp et al. 2021; Tsai et al. 2023; Bergero et al. 2023; Schäfer et al. 2019; Venkataraman et al. 2022; Bataille, 2020; Watari et al. 2022; Rosa and Gabrielli, 2023; Zhou and Herr, 2023; Costa et al. 2022; Dumas et al. 2022). While setting targets at the sectoral level expedite the achievement of national and well as global net-zero targets, it should be noted that the most efficient (i.e., cost-effective) way of achieving the 1.5°C target would be to set a net-zero target at the global level and let the countries trade emission reductions above their net-zero targets.

3. Critical Technologies for Net-Zero Emissions

Achieving the net-zero emissions target highly depends on the availability and affordability of some critical technologies (Davis et al. 2018). These include zero-emitting electricity generation technologies; end-use devices and processes using electricity; alternative technologies for structural materials (steel, cement). Moreover, some CO₂-intensive activities or services pose a greater challenge to achieving the net zero emission targets. These include aviation, long-distance road transportation, shipping, and carbon-intensive structural materials (e.g., steel and cement). Technologies, such as green hydrogen, energy storage, and CCS, which are not yet commercially available, would be critical to achieving the net zero emission targets. Many countries and non-state entities have considered these technologies in their net-zero roadmap assuming that these technologies will be

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available commercially in a decade or so (IEA, 2021; Williams et al. 2021; Rosa and Gabrielli, 2023; Watari et. 2022). Several studies (e.g., Zhou and Herr, 2023; IEA, 2022; IRENA, 2023; Renné, 2022; Schäfer et al. 2019) have examined the role of these technologies in meeting the net-zero targets at the global, regional, and national levels and estimate their economic costs.

Commercial availability of technologies, particularly carbon removal technologies, such as CCS/CCUS, BECCS, and DACCS will play a critical role in achieving the net zero targets in many countries. At the same time, large-scale energy storage facilities (e.g., batteries) will play an important role in decarbonizing the electricity supply system because, without a large-scale energy storage system, the full substitution of fossil fuel-based electricity with renewables is not possible. A commercial supply of green hydrogen is necessary for the decarbonization of the transportation sector. The success of commercial availability of these technologies mainly depends on how fast their costs drop. At present these technologies are prohibitively expensive with some exceptions, higher than the mean value of recently estimated social costs of carbon (\$185/tCO₂) (Rennert et al. 2022).

The costs of CCS vary across activities using fossil fuels. The cost of CO₂ capture alone varies in the range of \$15 - 25/tCO₂ in fuel transformation processes (e.g., coal to chemicals, natural gas processing) to \$50 - 120/tCO₂ in power generation, cement production, and iron and steel industries (IEA, 2020; Fuss et al. 2018). On top of it, costs of transportation and storage should be added which vary significantly across the project sites and type of storage (e.g., depleted oil reservoirs, ocean aquifers). As of the year 2022, there are 35 CCUS facilities commercially operating worldwide in industrial processes, fuel transformation, and power generation with a total capture capacity of almost 45 million tons of CO₂ annually (IEA 2022). The costs of BACCC vary from range from \$30/tCO₂ to 400/tCO₂ (Fuss et al. 2018). The lower value represents costs from the most suitable activities for BECCS due to the abundant supply of bioenergy sources, and the availability of CO₂ storage sites nearby the bioenergy sources (e.g., production of ethanol)¹. The higher costs refer to combustion technologies for energy production, such as biomass-based power generation.

The DACCS technologies are used to directly capture CO₂ from the atmosphere. But these technologies are not efficient because of their high input energy requirement, meaning that they cause CO₂ emissions through the energy they consume while capturing the atmospheric CO₂ if the input energy is not non-fossil fuel based. They are expensive when all input energy they require are supplied through green sources (green electricity or green hydrogen). Currently, there are only 17 DACCS plants worldwide with a total capacity of eight thousand tons of CO₂ per year. They are very small with the largest plant having a nominal capture capacity of 4,000 tons of CO₂/year (IEA, 2023). The costs of DACCS could vary from \$140/tCO₂ to \$1000/tCO₂ (2011 price) (Fuss et al. 2018).

The other technology critical to improving the reliability of renewable-based electricity supply systems is the large-scale battery storage system. The total installed capacity of utility-scale energy storage batteries was around 16 GW in 2021 as compared to more than 8000 GW of total electricity supply capacity worldwide². Based on several studies conducted since 2019, Cole et al. (2021) report that the costs of utility-scale batteries range from \$275/MWh to \$650/MWh. Similarly, the costs of green hydrogen range from \$1.2-

¹ Around 2.5 million tons of CO₂ is currently captured from bioenergy facilities annually around the world, of which more than 90% is from bioethanol plants (IEA, 2023).

² U.S. Energy Administration System Online database. <https://www.eia.gov/>

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2.1/kg when produced from steam methane reforming of natural gas with a CCS facility to \$3.2-7.7/kg when produced through electrolysis using renewable electricity.³ The lower range price of hydrogen produced from electrolysis using renewable electricity (i.e., \$3.2) is equivalent to \$22.6/GJ slightly higher than the \$19.8/GJ wholesale price of gasoline in New York (April 28, 2023)⁴.

The other challenge to these critical technologies is that they need minerals that have supply constraints. For example, the production of batteries for energy storage requires minerals such as lithium, nickel, cobalt, manganese, and graphite. Manufacturing electric vehicles and wind turbines requires rare earth elements such as neodymium, dysprosium, terbium and praseodymium. To stay in the net-zero emission path, it is estimated that the demand for copper and rare-earth elements will increase by 40% over the next two decades (IEA, 2022c). Similarly, the demand for nickel and cobalt will increase by 60-70%, and the demand for lithium will increase by 90% (IEA, 2022c). Moreover, the availability of these minerals is concentrated in a few countries, particularly China, which currently holds 30% of global processing for nickel, 60-70% for lithium and cobalt, and 90% for rare earth elements (IEA, 2023). The other countries that currently hold these materials significantly are Chile (lithium) and Indonesia (nickel).

4. Conclusions and Further Research

Since the Paris Climate Agreement, many nations, sub-nations, and corporate entities have announced net-zero emission targets. The targets are set for different years although 2050 is the most common year. In some countries, the net-zero targets are legally binding by their national laws, whereas these are voluntary or aspirational targets in others. These countries are developing roadmaps for achieving the targets. Setting national targets for net-zero emissions and developing roadmaps to achieve the targets are certainly welcome initiatives to meet the 1.5°C goal for climate change mitigation by the international community under the Paris Climate Agreement. However, how would the climate change mitigation activities aiming to achieve the net-zero targets affect the global, regional, national, and sub-national economies is an open question. Reviewing the existing body of knowledge, particularly available through peer-reviewed journal articles, we have come up with some conclusions.

First and foremost, since the net-zero targets have been recently announced, more time will be needed to understand the economic implications of meeting these targets. There are only a few studies examining the economic consequences of moving along the path of net-zero targets. Since the existing studies differ in terms of net-zero road maps considered, analytical tools used, current economic structures, and energy supply systems, their results vary widely. The vertical (income) and horizontal (spatial) distribution of the costs of achieving net-zero targets are critical while developing the roadmaps to achieve net-zero targets. However, no study has been done to understand the distributional consequences. Many more studies at the global, regional, national, and sub-national levels are needed to understand the macroeconomic and distributional impacts of scenarios to achieve the net zero targets.

³ <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/global-average-levelised-cost-of-hydrogen-production-by-energy-source-and-technology-2019-and-2050>

⁴ 1 kg of hydrogen contains 141.9 MJ of energy, whereas 1 kg of gasoline contains 45 MJ of energy. The wholesale price of gasoline in New York was \$2.57/gallon or \$ 0.9/kg on April 28, 2023.

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Second, existing studies are more focused on analyzing net-zero targets at sectoral levels (e.g., energy and power, transportation, manufacturing, building, and agriculture) even though net-zero targets are set at the national levels. However, net-zero targets at the sectoral level are sub-optimal. Global or national net-zero targets provide flexibility and reduce the overall costs. Surprisingly, studies are not available in this direction, and this is a big research gap. It is also important to know the level of carbon prices (e.g., universal carbon tax or floor carbon price) to achieve the net zero target globally within a given time frame, for example, by 2050.

Third, the available net-zero roadmaps suggest that most countries have a huge expectation from clean energy technologies, such as renewables with energy storage facilities (e.g., utility-scale batteries), green hydrogen and carbon removal technologies, such as carbon capture and storage or utilization from fossil fuels as well as biomass energy. But most of these technologies are highly expensive currently and are not available commercially. How fast and how much their costs will drop is uncertain although net-zero emission targets have given a signal to investing more in research and development on these technologies. Government policies, particularly fiscal incentives, could play a crucial role because government policies played the biggest role in reducing the costs of solar and wind and scaling up their deployment. Further research is needed on the design of effectiveness of policies that can help commercialize carbon removal, energy storage, and green hydrogen as well as other zero-carbon energy sources because the commercialization of these technologies is critical for achieving the net-zero targets.

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